

EFFECT OF DIGITALIZATION OF PRODUCT SALES ON SALES GROWTH IN NIGERIA

Ndionyenma, Samuel Chukwuemeka¹ and *Abugu, James Okechukwu²

¹*Department of Marketing. Faculty of Management Sciences. The University of America CURACAO*

²*Department of Marketing. Faculty of Business Administration. Enugu Campus, University of Nigeria, Nsukka.*

***Corresponding Author:** Abugu, James Okechukwu

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Keywords: digitalization, Product sales, website, email, social media sales growth.

Abstract: Technological waves is gaining much ground on how best to engage in business. This study seeks to empirically determine how digital selling aids in Sales Growth with Website Marketing, email marketing and social media Marketing as predictors. The study was carried out at Computer Village Ikeja, Lagos State Nigeria. Selected Vendors of Computers, allied products and other ICT accessories as well as requires who engage in digital selling formed the population of the study. Sample size of 386 drawn from the study population were issued with questionnaire to elicit necessary information from them. After the collection, presentation and analysis of data collected from them and test of the study hypotheses, it was established that website marketing, email marketing and social media marketing respectively has significant positive effect on sales growth. It was thus concluded that digital tools such as website, email and social media significantly enhance sales growth and therefore recommended that organisations or vendors especially those of computers and ICTS should apply website marketing, email marketing and social media marketing to enhance sales growth.

Introduction

Technology plays vital role in product sales-through stream lining processes, enhancing communication and providing valuable data insights. Apart from this, technology provides many forms of apps as tools for facilitating exchange. With the aid of such technological tools, customers can browse digital product catalogues, shops or even make inquires through

phones, the distance notwithstanding. It has been established that as customers increasingly interact with organizations through digital channels, the shift tends to create significant opportunities for sales and marketing functions to enhance and streamline operations. Cody (2024), affirmed that sales technologies boost the efficiency and productivity of sales team by automating routine tasks, facilitating lead

generation managing customer relationship and improving sales outcomes.

Product sales can be effected physically or online and even both. However, the digital channel for product sales seems to portray direct or physical sales inform of personal selling as not being capable of capturing reasonable customers, thus could negatively affect sales growth. Digitalization has brought to bear many available methods to reach target audience. The act of converting traditional sales processes into digital one using technology to improve efficiency as well as customer experience is what digitalization of product sales is all about. Zhai et al (2022) describe digital as a global trend that is spreading throughout economic sectors. John (2025) affirmed that online sales channel has redefined traditional commerce by providing businesses with diverse mediums to engage with consumers in the virtual sphere. Navigating the digital realm however, presents a persistent challenge due to inherent security risks like data breaches, cyber-attack and identity theft (Ibrahim et al, 2020).

The technological barriers of online or digitalization sales according to Sanchez-Riofrio et al (2022) is that small enterprises may counter challenges in maintaining current infrastructure platforms and software induced by limited technological resources impeding the businesses from fully capitalizing on the potential benefits offered by online sales channels thus affect the competitiveness in the digital market place. Worldwide, the wave of the application of technology in virtually all sphere of life is

increasing at geometric progression. In Nigeria a number of Dealers on products engage in digital selling. Appraising the outcome of this engagement in relation to sales growth is worthwhile. This study was however promoted by the sparse of study on the effect of digital selling on sales growth in popular computer village at Ikeja, Lagos, Nigeria. The main objective of this study is to establish the effect of digitalization of product sales on sales growth at the computer village Ikeja Lagos, Nigeria. Thus we hypothesized, that;

- i. Product sales through website has no significant effect on sales growth at Computer Village Ikeja Lagos Nigeria
- ii. Product sales through Email has no significant effect on sales growth at Computer Village Ikeja Lagos Nigeria
- iii. Product sales through social media has no significant effect on sales growth at computer village, Ikeja, Lagos Nigeria.

Literature Review

Conceptual Review

Website and Product Sales

Website makes provision for creating an online storefront, displaying product and facilitating sales organisations. Erdal (2023) contended that e-commerce businesses should design their websites according to the wishes and needs of their customers. YEC (2020) stated that having a strong online presence-particularly can be make or break for generating more revenue. Farhang et al (2012) proclaimed that website information convenience plays very important role in success of companies in competition through e-

commerce, thus, this factor leads the companies to have competitive edge and be successful in achieving their final goal. The ever increase of information on the web has the potential to result in more knowledgeable customers who are able to make better decisions and will experience more satisfaction with their purchase (Hurme, 2005).

Website convenience advantage as inferred by Zhu and Kraemer (2002) suggests that some customers may have a limited time so they can save time and take the advantage of the convenience of buying online. A good number of websites exist each providing cue to attract patronage.

Kim (2002) stated that websites can record customer surfing paths or buying history to enable websites provide suggestions for customerization for further purchases. As opined by Desatruck (2006), the provision of sufficient and convenience information through website contributes a lot of savings in customers valuable time which can attract many customers. Fox (2001) stated that one of the ways to provide the best for customers is through attractive website appearance. Creation of sense of comfort when visiting the website to view products, will possibly encourage buying decisions by visitors (Gutama et al, 2021) Brandy (2024) affirmed that a website (like informational website) is the essential first step in making business easily discoverable. Further that a well-designed website is a convenient pointer for online activities from sales to stock updates. In a similar submission, Zheng, Cheung Lee and Liang

(2015) opined that Marketers and developers need to create easily-to –use and dedicated to the result websites (like interactive websites) so as to enhance engagement, essentially enabling customers have easy access to tracking members or boosting parcels for delivering which result to the invention or creation of brand loyalty.

Wortz et al (2019) emphatically stated that worldwide web (www) artificial intelligence (AI) Mobile devices documents, fluctuating customers interest and usage habits accelerate network expansion. Sakas et al (2020) explained that websites lead fast and can boost user experience and reciprocally increase the brand name. Chitkara and Mahmood (2020) noted that websites play significant role in business success since a website traffic performance can be extracted and get measured so as to optimize digital marketing strategy. Website according to Vogelzang (2016) are valuable tools to reach potential customers and retain the existing ones. ITIF (2021) contended that websites aid greatly when it comes to greater visibility and brand awareness.

Email Platforms and Product Sales

Email platforms are akin to promote and sell products. The email features such as automation analytics and segmentation help drive Sales and engage customers. Ray (2021) stated that Email marketing or promotional email is the strategic use of email campaigns to promote products or services, nurture customer relationships and drive business growth. That it as well allows brands to deliver tailored messages straight to the boxes of potential and actual customers, thus

building trust and encouraging repeat purchases. Drell (2011) argued that e-mail marketing is part of outbound marketing, a one-way means of messaging that relies on companies send information to the consumers for purposes of getting their attention. Micheaux (2013) affirmed that consumers can perceive pressure by receiving e-mail marketing. Email like newsletter email can be used to attract customers through sending personalized messages and developing a relationship with customers that will create brand loyalty, brand awareness and increase brand equity. (Rohma et al, 2024) Email marketing has the potential to improve the relationship between the organization and the customers and promote the reputation of the business and aid customer loyalty. Adikesavan (2014) contended that email such as transactional email can play an important role in the adopted marketing strategy when it comes to lead generation, brand awareness, relationship building or retaining customers across different types of marketing process.

Social Media and Sales Growth

It has been affirmed that by using social media platforms such as facebook, WhatSapp, Instagram businesses can create meaningful interactions with consumers. Backer, Nobre and Kanabar (2013) stated that social media marketing refers to the application of a social media platform to promote a product or service for the purpose of increasing its visibility on the internet.

Describing the major functions of some popular social media platforms, Popp et al (2016) argued

that face book is known for its robust platform for customer relationship management. Culotta and Cutler (2016) emphasized that Twitter is known for its ability to communicate brand messages and quick consumer responses in real time. Instagram focuses on sharing image-based content (Munoz and Towner, 2017) Indvik (2011) affirmed that Youtube is a platform for sharing videos. Salem and Salem (2019) made it clear that social media allows customers to find useful information about other brands and if conforms to the expectations of the customers, it can lead to a switch and continuous purchase of the brand(s). Olabanji (2014) stated that social media platform aids in the promotion of the organizations goods and services as well as the brand. In the realm of business world, traditional media marketing is being phased out in favour of social media marketing (Omotayo, et al, 2015).

Theoretical Framework

Two theories guide this study; namely; Technology Acceptance Model, (TAM) and Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA)

Technological Acceptance Model (TAM)

The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), introduced by Davis in 1989, is a theory widely used to understand how users come to accept and use technology. According to the model, perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness are the two primary factors influencing users' decision to adopt a new technology. In the context of this study, the TAM can be applied to understand how business perceive and integrate digital marketing tools like Website, Email and Social Media into their brand building strategies.

Perceived usefulness refers to the degree to which a tool or technology is believed to enhance performance or productivity. In terms of product sales, tools like website, Email and social media provide businesses with insights into consumer behavior, conversion rates, and engagement metrics, making them highly useful for refining marketing strategies. By helping businesses better understand their customers, the aforementioned tools allow for more targeted campaigns that can improve brand awareness and customer loyalty (Alwan & Alshurideh, 2022).

Perceived ease of use, on the other hand, pertains to the extent to which a technology is easy to use and integrate into existing workflows. Website, Email and Social media offer user-friendly interfaces. As noted by Hollebeek and Macky (2019), the ease of use of these tools enables marketers to spend less time on technical aspects and more time focusing on sales strategy and engagement. This ease of integration helps businesses maintain consistency in their sales and communication efforts, further contributing to the strengthening of sales growth and overall business performance.

TAM's application to this study is evidenced on how businesses adopt and use digital marketing tools. The more useful and easy to use these tools are perceived to be, the more likely they are to be embraced, leading to better campaign performance and by extension, enhanced sales growth.

Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA)

The theory of reasoned action was developed by Fishbein in 1980. The theory aims at predicting individual intentions to engage particular behavior at a specific time and within diverse context. Abugu and Musa (2021) maintained that the mainstream of TRA is the intention given rise to certain action, attitude, a motivational construct that is regarded the immediate, closest or proximal influence of certain behavior. In relation to this study, the Dealers use digital marketing tools as promotion tools to educate and convince customers to buy and the customers use the digital tool due to usefulness of the messages therein regarding products being sought for purchase, this resulting to sales growth.

The study is anchored on TAM and TRA, this is because the two theories provide strong theoretical underpinnings for understanding the relationship between digitalization for product sales and sales growth. Whereas TAM perceived ease of use attract customers, the usefulness component of TAM is for both vendors and the customers. By inference to the study, the digital tools attract customers and provide customers avenue on the functionality of the digital tools and direct their choice. That of TRA when inferred, suggests that the vendors use digital tools to make sales whereas the tools expose customers to arrays of products and in this context, aid on the best product to be purchased.

Study Model

Independent Variable

H1

H2

H3

Digital Marketing Tools

Dependent Variable

Fig 2.1- Digital Marketing Tools induced sales growth (DMISGRO) 2025

Figure 2.1 above portrays how Digital Marketing tools (website, Email and Social Media induce sales growth.

Methodology

Research Design

The research design for the study was survey method.

Area of the study

The study was conducted in Computer village, Ikeja Lagos, Nigeria where computer and allied products are sold.

Population of the study

The population comprised of selected vendors of computers allied products (such as Laptops, mobile phones and other ICT products and accessories) as well as repairers who engage in digital selling and their customers.

Sample size and Sampling Technique

The study adopted Cochran's formula to determine the sample size of 386 respondents for the study. Convenience sampling method was used to select those who indicated interest to participate in the study.

Research Instrument

Structural questionnaire was the instrument used to elicit relevant data from the respondents. The responses to the questions, directed to the respondents were on five-points likert scale of 5,4, 3, 2 and 1 and aligne to strongly agree, agree fairly agree, disagree and strongly disagree respectively. Content validity of the instrument was done to ensure that the instrument covered the objectives of the study. For the internal

consistence, of the instrument Cronbach alpha formula was used, resulting to 0.70 thus confirming the suitability of the instrument for the study.

Data Presentation and Analysis

Out of a total of copies of the questionnaire issued to the respondents only 346. Copies were correctly completed, returned and were used for the study.

The data collected for the study were presented in tables and analysed as below.

4.1 Responses on Effect of Websites on Sales growth:

Question	Descriptions	SD%	D%	IND%	A%	SA	Total%
1	Rate accordingl y Information website attracted me to buy the Android phone am using now	55(16%)	35 (10.2%)	50 (14.5%)	86 (25.1%)	120 (34.9%)	346 (100%)
2	Rate accordingl y Interactive website is ideal to be visited to choose the best technology	15 (4.4%)	30 (8.7%)	25 (7.3%)	139 (40.4%)	135 (39.2%)	346 (100%)
3	Rate accordingl y E-commerce website guided me on the laptop I purchased	20 (5.8%)	30 (8.7%)	54 (15.7%)	116 (33.7%)	124 (36%)	344 (100%)
4	Rate accordingl y Company's website always attract my purchase action at computer village	15 (4.4%)	30 (8.7%)	40 (11.6%)	130 (37.8%)	129 (37.5%)	346 (1.00%)
Average		27 (7.9%)	31 (9.0%)	60 (12.9%)	132 (22.4%)	124 (46%)	346 (100%)

Source: Survey Data, 2025

The analysis in table 4.1 above shows that on the average 27 (7.9%) respondents strongly disagreed, 31(9.0%) of the respondents disagreed, 60 (12.9%) indifferences, 132 (22.4%) and 124 (46.7%) of the respondents agreed and strongly agreed. This shows that websites have significant positive effect on

the sales growth as 58 (16.9%) respondents both strongly disagreed and disagreed. While 256.6(68.4%) respondents either agreed or strongly agreed.

Table 4.2 Responses on the Effect of Emails on Sales growth.

Question	Descriptions	SD%	D%	IND%	A%	SA	Total%
1	Rate accordingly Promotional Email attract customers to buy phones	40(11.6%)	30 (8.7%)	44 (12.8%)	80(23.3%)	150 (43.6%)	346 (100%)
2	Rate accordingly Newsletter issued to actual and potential customers attracted their patronage	20 (5.8%)	40 (11.4%)	40 (11.6%)	16 (33.7%)	130 (37.8%)	346 (1000%)
3	Rate accordingly Transactional email is used to direct and win individual customers at computer village	50 (14.5%)	40 (11.6%)	46 (13.4%)	90 (26.2%)	120 (34.9%)	346 (100%)
4	Rate accordingly Welcome email provided information and attracted customers' patronage	40 (11.6%)	30 (8.7%)	50 (14.5%)	76 (22.1%)	150 (43.6%)	346 (1.00%)
Average		39.2 (11.4%)	34 ((9.9%)	44 (12.8%)	46.2 (22.4%)	135.2 (46%)	346 (100%)

Source: Survey Data, 2025

The contents of table 4.2 above shows that on the average 39.2 (10.2%) respondents strongly disagreed, 34 (9.9%) of the respondents disagreed, 44.3 (12.8%) indifference, 46.2 (23.7%) and 135.2 (15.5%) of the respondents agreed and strongly agreed. This shows that email has significant positive effect on the

sales growth of products at computer village 181.4 (52.31%) respondents agreed and strongly agreed. While 73.2 (21.3%) respondents either disagreed or strongly disagreed.

Table 4.3 Responses on the Effect of Social Media Platforms

Ques	Descriptions	SD%	D%	IND%	A%	SA	Total%
1	Rate accordingly Face book provides me with letter guide to make wise purchase at computer village	40(11.6%)	45 (13.1%)	55 (16.%)	74 (21.5%)	130 (37.8%)	346 (100%)
2	Rate accordingly You tube is source of my reference when making purchase	30 (5.7%)	40 (11.4%)	40 (11.6%)	110 (32.%)	124 (36.%)	346 (1000%)
3	Rate accordingly WhatSAPP linkage is the greatest source of our increased sales.	20 (5.7%)	40 (11.6%)	50 (14.5%)	80 (23.3%)	144 (41.9%)	346 (1.00%)
4	Rate accordingly Blogging increased my customer base	40 (11.6%)	50 (14.5%)	20 (5.7%)	80 (23.3%)	144 (41.9%)	346 (1.00%)
Average		32 (11.6%)	43 ((12.4%)	43 (12.4%)	87.2 (25.2)	132 (38.2%)	346 (100%)

Source: Survey Data, 2025

Considering table 4.3, on the average, 32 99.2%) respondents strongly disagreed, 43 (12.4%) of the respondents disagreed, 43 (12.4%) indifference, 87.2 (25.2%) and 132 (63.4%) of the respondents agreed and strongly agreed. Thus, indicating that social media platforms has significant positive effect on sales growth as 75 (22%), respondents strongly disagreed and disagreed. While 130.2 (37.6%) respondents either agreed or strongly agreed.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis One

H_{0i}: Website has significant positive effect on sales growth in computer village Ikeja, Lagos.

Regression

Table 4.4 Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	Std. Error of The Estimate
1	.989a	.979	.978	.20282

Predictors: (Constant), The Vendors and repairers at Computer Village with information about their services. The customers at the computer village are keen to establishing friendly relationships with the Vendors.

The Vendors and repairers at the computer village are keen to find solutions for correct purchase action. The vendors at the computer village are keen to identifying the desires and needs of customers.

Table 4.1.1 ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig
1 Regression	635.611	4	158.903	3863.049	.000 ^b
Residual	13.944	339	.041		
Total	649.555	343			

Dependent Variable: The Vendors has requirements of customers thus will lead to sales growth.

b. Predictors: (Constant), The concerned Vendors and repairers in computer village provide buyers with information about the items sold. The vendor at the computer village are keen to establish friendly relationships with customers. The Vendors at the computer village are keen to find solutions to customers problems. The Vendors and repairers at the computer village are keen to identify the desires and needs of the customers.

Table 4.1.2. Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig
		B	Std. Erro	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.020	.022	.28	11.185	.000
	Information website attracted me to buy the	.360	.032	.354	-2.283	.023

Android phone am using now					
Interactive website is ideal to be visited to choose the best technology	.076	.033	.076	9.601	.000
E-Commerce guided me on the lap top I purchased	.404	.042	.416	6.199	.000
Company's website always attract my purchase action at computer village.	.295	.048	.304		
Dependent Variable: Sales Growth					

From the analysis website has a significant positive effect on Sales growth at computer village, Ikeja Lagos. This has a p-value 0.000 which is less than 0.05 with coefficient value of .028. This shows that website has a significant positive effect on sales growth. Thus we conclude that website has significant positive effect on sales growth at computer village Lagos.

Hypothesis Two

Product Sales through E-mail has no significant effect on sales growth in computer village Ikeja, Lagos..

Table 4.13. Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of The Estimate
1	1.000 ^a	1.000	.1000	.00000

Predictors: (Constant), Email marketing make use of various types eg Promotional email, Welcome email, transactional email which aids company's sales growth.

Table 4.1.4. ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1. Regression	688.997	2	344.499	2863.049	.000 ^b
Residual	581.789	342	.3x3(12.345)		
Total	688.997	344			

Predictors: (Constant), Email Marketing makes use of various types of tools like promotional email, newsletter transactional email to promote products or services and build customer relationship resulting to sales growth.

Table 4.1.5 Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	.030	.032	.038	13.185	.000
Promotional Email attract customers to buy phone	.310	.032	.314	13.185	.000
Newsletter issued to actual and potential customers attract patronage ;	.176	.133	.176	-3.283	.023
Transactional email is used to direct and win individual customers at computer village	.414	.142	.416	8.601	.000
Welcome email provides more information and attract patronage	.395	.148	.104	7.199	.000
a. Dependent Variable: Sales Growth					

Based on the analysis Email marketing has a significant positive effect on sales growth with a p-value 0.000 which is less than 0.05 with coefficient value of .018. This shows that Email marketing has a significant positive effect on sales growth at Computer village Lagos. With this we conclude that Email marketing has a significant positive effect on sales growth at Computer village Lagos.

Hypothesis Three

Product sales through social media has significant positive effect on sales growth at computer village Ikeja Lagos.

Table 4.1.6. Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of The Estimate
1	1.000 ^a	1.000	.1000	.00000

a. Predictors: (Constant), I prefer if the social media support chart groups. I suggest if they update customers about change associated with transaction. I suggest if they spend time on communication with customers.

Table 4.1.7. ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1. Regression	649.555	2	324.778	2863.049	.000 ^b
Residual	.318.213	342	.322.890		
Total	649.555	344			

a. Dependent Variable: Sales Growth

a. Predictors: (constant) I prefer if the social media support chart groups. I suggest if they update customers about change associated with transaction. Also, if they spend time on communication with customers.

Table 4.1.8 Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(constant)	.020	.022	.28	.11.185	.000
1	Face book provides me with letter guide to make wise purchase at computer village	.060	.032	.354	-2.283	.000
	You tube is source of my reference when making purchase	.076	.033	.076	9.601	.000
	Whatsapp linkage is the greatest source of our increased sales.	.404	.142	.416	6.199	.023

Blogging increased my customer base	.295	.148	.304	.000
Average	.395	.148	.104	.000

From the analysis social media has a significant positive effect on Sales growth at computer village Ikeja Lagos. This has a p-value 0.000 which is less than 0.05 with coefficient value of .028. This shows that social media has a significant effect on sales growth. Thus we conclude that social media has significant positive effect on sales growth at computer village Lagos.

Findings and Discussion of Findings

Among the major findings of the study was that website significantly and positively, has effect on sales growth. ANOVA test on this showed a p-value 0.000 which is less than 0.05 with coefficient value of .028, considered significant Mahmood is in agreement with the finding when he noted that websites play significant role in business success since a website traffic performance can be extracted and get measured so as to optimize digital marketing strategy. In agreement on this, Vogelzang (2016) pointed out that website are valuable Email platform was discovered to have significant positive effect on product sales growth. The ANOVA test on this showed significant result on the variables with a p-value 0.000 which is less than 0.05 with coefficient value of .081. This result aligned with the view of Ray (2021) that Email marketing promote product or services, nurture customer relationship and drive business growth. The study equally confirmed that social media has

significant positive effect on sales growth. The test using ANOVA showed a p-value 0.000 which is less than 0.05 with coefficient value of 0.28. The outcome is consistent with the views of Pepp et al (2016) Culota (2016) Munog and Towner (2017), that social media platforms greatly aid sales growth.

Conclusion

The study sought to unravel the effect of digital tools on sales growth using Website, Email and social media as predictors. These tools based on the investigation carried out, respectively demonstrated significant positive effect on sales growth. The researchers thus conclude that digitalization of product Sales has significant positive effect on sales growth.

Recommendation

- i. Business and Marketers should use website Marketing to accelerate sales growth
- ii. Email marketing should be used for purposes of increasing sales growth
- iii. Social media platform should be used to achieve sales growth.

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